

This document include the complete tables of our topic model results.

Table A1: The top 10 terms in the 24 topics clustering 6 major SE phases as found by this research

Cluster #	Cluster Label	Topic #	Manual label	Top 10 terms
1	Maintenance	Topic 1	taint analysis	analysi, execut, analyz, taint, result, hypercal, compar, becom, inform, lightweight
		Topic 2	fuzzy logic	program, input, fuzz, explor, base, path, real, symbol, stage, limit,
		Topic 4	detecting overflow	detect, technique, overflow, automat, buffer, fals, earli, static, posit, analysi
		Topic 7	attack mechanism	attack, approach, browser, base, firewall, request, detect, implement, present, includ
		Topic 10	web application	applic, web, access, control, state, client, check, world, make, real
		Topic 13	bugs and release analysis	bug, releas, research, analysi, increase, non, empir, examin, associ, differ
		Topic 23	static analysis	static, valid, cross, input, script, site, propos, string, common, dynam
2	Source Code	Topic 8	security design	secur, threat, approach, function, design, base, engine, level, process, featur
		Topic 5	security study	secur, report, problem, studi, process, reliabl, fix, collect, detect, discuss
		Topic 19	development	develop, secur, improve, practice, priorit, evalu, context, find, defin, framework
		Topic 21	source code	code, sourc, develop, open, contain, line, linux, integ, perform, transform
3	Testing	Topic 6	system analysis	system, use, base, analysi, signatur, forma, specif, metric, architecture, scenario
		Topic 11	test cases	test, generat, case, result, use, effect, algorithm, xssvs, data, complex
		Topic 20	software security	softwar, provid, part, time, statist, reduc, general, combin, exploit, secur
		Topic 22	exploit	exploit, system, paper, mitig, challeng, worm, defens, diagnosi, major, memori
4	Modeling	Topic 12	malware methods	method, malwar, use, show, behavior, learn, detect, malici, comput, featur
		Topic 18	patch study	vendor, disclosur, patch, time, respons, show, sever, valu, releas, studi
		Topic 24	prediction model	model, predict, paper, evalu, propos, use, compon, methodology, issu, effort
5	Risk Analysis	Topic 9	risk estimation	inform, risk, avail, estim, potenti, oper, cvss, allow, data, provid
		Topic 17	project repository	data, identify, project, repository, inform, sourc, relat, across, exist, research
6	Tool	Topic 3	binary tool	tool, binary, user, mani, emonstr, creat, present, engine, structur, crash
		Topic 16	sql injection	inject, sql, database, identify, slice, tool, work, xml, type, obtain
7	Other	Topic 14	version assessment	version, investing, assess, caus, autom, trace, anomali, surfac, current, approxim
		Topic 15	vulnerability discovery	vulner, discov, discoveri, type, signific, known, order, result, exist, flow

Table A2: The 24 topics discovered by LDA

Topic name	Top 10 terms
security study	secur, report, problem, studi, process, reliabl, fix, collect, detect, discuss
prediction model	model, predict, paper, evalu, propos, use, compon, methodology, issu, effort
bugs and release analysis	bug, releas, research, analysi, increase, non, empir, examin, associ, differ
static analysis	static, valid, cross, input, script, site, propos, string, common, dynam
system analysis	system, use, base, analysi, signatur, forma, specif, metric, architecture, scenario
test cases	test, generat, case, result, use, effect, algorithm, xssvs, data, complex
web application	applic, web, access, control, state, client, check, world, make, real
project repository	data, identify, project, repository, inform, sourc, relat, across, exist, research
detecting overflow	detect, technique, overflow, automat, buffer, fals, earli, static, posit, analysi
vulnerability discovery	vulner, discov, discoveri, type, signific, known, order, result, exist, flow
patch study	vendor, disclosur, patch, time, respons, show, sever, valu, releas, studi
malware	method, malwar, use, show, behavior, learn, detect, malici, comput, featur
exploit	exploit, system, paper, mitig, challeng, worm, defens, diagnosi, major, memori
risk estimation	inform, risk, avail, estim, potenti, oper, cvss, allow, data, provid
attack mechanism	attack, approach, browser, base, firewall, request, detect, implement, present, includ
taint analysis	analysi, execut, analyz, taint, result, hypercal, compar, becom, inform, lightweight
development	develop, secur, improve, practice, priorit, evalu, context, find, defin, framework
fuzzy logic	program, input, fuzz, explor, base, path, real, symbol, stage, limit,
binary tool	tool, binary, user, mani, emonstr, creat, present, engine, structur, crash
sql injection	inject, sql, database, identify, slice, tool, work, xml, type, obtain
source code	code, sourc, develop, open, contain, line, linux, integ, perform, transform
version assessment	version, investing, assess, caus, autom, trace, anomali, surfac, current, approxim
security design	secur, threat, approach, function, design, base, engine, level, process, featur
software security	softwar, provid, part, time, statist, reduc, general, combin, exploit, secur

Table A3: Topic shares and trends

Topic name	Popularity (%)	Trend (<i>p-value</i>)	Topic name	Popularity (%)	Trend (<i>p-value</i>)
security study	1.728699	↑	exploit	0.869622	↓
prediction model	1.560169	↑	risk estimation	0.861604	↓
bugs and release analysis	1.513145	↓	attack mechanism	0.861546	↓
static analysis	1.459491	↓	taint analysis	0.849078	↓
system analysis	1.416026	↓	development	0.837696	↑
test cases	1.240476	↓	fuzzy logic	0.82735	↓
web application	1.233553	↓	binary tool	0.820848	↓
project repository	1.192519	↓	sql injection	0.67591	↓
detecting overflow	1.157353	↓	source code	0.665216	↓
vulnerability discovery	1.038362	↑	version assessment	0.639975	↓
patch study	0.925041	↑	security design	0.532554	↓
malware	0.911013	↓	software security	0.494215	↓